

SPHINX

Site: TEMPLE Season GS 79-80

Area: N. COLONNADE Square R16 Locus Number (3c)

Progress of Excavation 24/I/80 R16A1: Cleared out 3c:

banked alongside 4-4d down to bit of 4d on floor in
narrow space W side of trench. This definitely not same
as 3b. A.G. brings up tiny bit newspaper from sifting
Some question - could have come from (2a) (balk trimming)

31/I/80: R16A2. (3a) "encircles (3b) + on to S.T. N wall at NE corner.
Slopes down against (3b) to W side trench. Lower part, large
granite frag on surface (3c)-(3b) line // (3c) Removed. Sifted.
From clearing shows that (3b) itself runs to S.T. wall in NE corner

Locus Description DAMP BROWN SAND

Location in Square VV SIDE

Under Locus (2) CLEAN SAND Over Locus 4-4d

Locus Dimensions _____

Levels _____

Analysis of non-artifactual materials Few limestone frags, couple
fair sized dolomite chips, sherd frags (small ND), granite chips.

of trench) up to, over slightly, ledge cut in c.b. (for granite sheathing. (3c) contains some granite, alabaster, etc. stone material fine to small limestone frags. Few shreds. 1 small diagnostic.